

What a classic neurological examination involves?

Neurologist [David Schick](#) explains that the first step of a typical neurological visit involves a short interview related to the symptoms.

Schick shares that the short interview on the symptoms allows the neurologist to get a brief idea of the present problem.

The second step is the medical history.

Through the anamnesis, [experienced neurologist](#) David Schick collects a series of facts of medical interest relating to the patient, such as: the general state of health, diseases suffered in the past, habits, work activity, motor activities practiced in free time and any recurring illnesses in the family.

The anamnesis directs the neurologist to the possible causes at the origin of the symptoms complained of by the patient.

David Schick indicates that the third and final step includes a thorough physical examination and the aforementioned neurological examination.

Through the physical examination, the neurologist David Schick carefully analyzes the patient's body, looking for symptoms and signs related to a general suffering of the organism.

Through the neurological examination, on the other hand, David Schick evaluates the cognitive and motor skills of the patient, testing, depending on the circumstances, reflexes, muscle strength, coordination, sensory functions, language, etc. For a consultation, [contact the specialist](#) David Schick.